

Extreme science: Exploring the use of extreme-terrain rovers in Mars Sample Return

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Abstract—The NASA Mars Exploration Program is developing mission concepts for the capture and return of diverse geological and atmospheric samples from Mars to Earth. The first phase of a hypothetical multi-year sample-return campaign is the collection and caching of the samples; the second phase would center on the retrieval of the cached samples and launch of the cache into Mars’ orbit, with the third phase being responsible for the capture of the orbiting sample(s) and their return to Earth.

The second phase is known as the Sample Retrieval and Launch (SRL) concept, which would require a dedicated rover to retrieve the previously-cached samples for launch into Martian orbit, and subsequent return to Earth.

Our contribution assesses the feasibility of conducting an extreme-terrain exploration mission in the extended-phase, following the launch of the cache into orbit. Our study leverages prior development of the MobileMAV concept, which uses Mars Science Laboratory (MSL)-based mobility to carry the Mars Ascent Vehicle (MAV)[1]. Our proposal is driven by the scientific value of exploring various challenging topographies such as recurring slope lineae (RSLs), craters, fissures, canyons, gullies, caves, and stratified terrain. These geologic features are expected to contain a wealth of scientific information that would greatly advance scientific understanding of dynamic processes in the Martian environment. The ability to operate on (and in) these challenging areas (and their environs) would also aid in the search for habitable environments, and significantly shorten the path to human-driven Martian exploration.

The core contribution is an investigation of a trade space that would integrate a two-wheel, tethered rappelling rover (based on the Axel extreme-terrain rover [2]) into the mobileMAV concept, capturing the key benefits and risks to the overall mission. Although introducing new rover designs reduces our ability to leverage flight-tested heritage hardware, the possibility of dramatically extending the science capabilities — while simultaneously achieving the primary mission goal of delivering the MAV to the launch site — would be compelling.

We present a conceptual design that is, to first-order, compatible with the existing MSL launch, cruise, and entry, descent and landing (EDL) baseline. We require minimal changes to the existing architecture to accommodate the rover and MAV payload. Although some challenges exist with respect to flown weight (greater than MSL) and available avionics payload (smaller than MSL), the required technological advances appear well within the projected arc of technology development, given the proposed mission concept timeline.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Within a notional MSR flight campaign concept, there would be three distinct flight missions. The first of these, the Sample Caching Rover (SCR), would be dedicated to exploring compelling science targets on Mars and building up a cache of valuable geologic (and atmospheric) data for further analysis on Earth. The second mission, and the focus of this paper, would be the SRL mission concept. The scope of this hypothetical mission would be to retrieve the cached samples and transfer the cached and sealed samples to the Mars Ascent Vehicle. The final-phase Sample Return Orbiter would subsequently capture the orbiting sample cache (that would be the only thing left from the MAV), and return the samples to the vicinity of Earth.

Preliminary conceptual designs for the SRL architecture envisioned a small, Mars Exploration Rover (MER)-sized *fetch* rover which retrieves the samples from the cache site, and returns them to a stationary launcher. While such an architecture would result in a smaller rover, the round trip back to the stationary MAV would double the traverse distance and hence the duration of the mission.

In [1] the authors explore the use of a *mobile-MAV*; in this design, the rover transports the MAV to the cache site for subsequent launch. This greatly reduces the required traverse range of the rover, with the added complexity of transporting the launch vehicle.

Prior studies of the mobile-MAV concept have not focused on science instruments and, particularly, post-MAV launch capabilities from the SRL vehicle. In contrast, we explicitly evaluate the vehicle as a science platform for conducting higher-risk science in the post MAV-launch phase. The difficulty and effort involved in deploying a vehicle on Mars makes a compelling argument for utilizing it to its fullest extent, conditional on the completion of the primary goal of the mission.

In this paper, we consider the dual goals of safe MAV traverse

and launch, as well as the ability to conduct an extreme-terrain science-driven mission. In the following section we consider the advantages of conducting science in challenging terrain.

2. MISSION CONCEPT REQUIREMENTS

Consider Holden crater in Figure 1, a candidate site for Mars 2020. Holden crater provides various compelling scientific areas within the proposed landing ellipse, including alluvial fans, flood-deposits, bedrock outcrops and stratified sediments ideal for the search for organic material.

Figure 1: Holden crater, a prime Mars 2020 candidate. The notional landing ellipse is in the south-western quadrant of the crater.

Promising targets further afield require an extended-phase mission concept; for example, consider Holden targets 5 and 6, shown in Figure 2:

Figure 2: Holden 5 and 6, candidate sites for the extended-phase mission. These sites are approximately 20 km from the center of the nominal ellipse.

As can be seen from Figure 2, the targets proposed for the extended phase are well outside the mission ellipse - sites 5 and 6 are 20 km from the nominal center. Figure 3 shows a closer view of Holden 5:

Visible in Figure 3 is the distinct stratification of the terrain. These layers would provide an excellent window into the spatio-temporal nature of geology of the area, and greatly advance the understanding of dynamic processes in the Martian environment.

Holden 6 is the putative site of a former hydrothermal envi-

Figure 3: Holden 5, a site candidate for the extended-phase. Note the exposed stratigraphic layers, an attractive scientific prospect.

Figure 4: Holden 6, possible site of a former hydrothermal environment. Acquiring samples from this site requires a rover with extreme-terrain capability.

ronment, as evidenced by sedentary heterogeneous deposits (megabreccia) as well as light tones in the surrounding rock. Accessing these sites would require a rover capable of traversing challenging terrain.

Consider another candidate landing site for Mars 2020 - Jezero crater, shown in Figure 5:

Figure 5: Jezero crater, a Mars 2020 candidate landing site. Overlaid are various landing ellipses: MSL baseline (yellow), range-triggered (blue) and range-triggered/Terrain-Relative Navigation (green). Use of TRN and range-triggered parachute deployment allows for “land-on” science capabilities.

Jezero crater is the potential site of a former paleolake, with a delta that is a promising location to search for preserved organic matter. Highlighted in the figure are the 3σ landing ellipses for various EDL modes - MSL nominal (yellow), range-triggered (RT) (blue), and range-triggered combined

with Terrain-Relative Navigation (green). Refinements in landing capability afforded by the combination of range-triggered parachute deployment and TRN enable “land-on” science for 2020, and significantly reduce the traverse distance for the SRL rover.

However, accessing the promising inlet valleys (marked in Figure 5) would require leaving the relatively benign crater basin and operating in more complex topographies, shown in Figure 6):

Figure 6: Jezero slope profile. Note the slope of the terrain surrounding the rim of the crater; accessing the surrounding valleys requires a rover capable of extreme-terrain mobility.

Given the topography of the crater, accessing the deltas would require a vehicle that is capable of sustained operation in complex, challenging terrain. We now consider the notion of extreme-terrain mobility, and robust solutions in this space.

3. EXTREME-TERRAIN MOBILITY (ETM)

Given the attractive scientific nature of areas with complex topographies, we require a reliable, robust mobility system capable of sustained operation in such environments. Mobility concepts with extreme-terrain capability have been explored in the literature, ranging from walking vehicles [3], to hopping platforms [4][5], to hybrid systems [6]. A fundamental underlying challenge with many of these approaches is that of increasing complexity; the systems required for a legged vehicle, for example, require a much higher degree of sophistication than that of a wheeled vehicle. For space applications, the need for redundancy and reliability often preclude the use of more complex designs and the mobility they afford. Other concerns include total platform mass, energy usage with respect to distance travelled, and the ability to sample and analyze scientific instrument data.

We propose the use of an alternative robust, redundant mobility design known as Axel, shown below [7]:

Figure 7 shows Axel during a field trial, deploying a UV reflectance spectrometer and microscopic imager on a cliff face. Axel is designed to be operated in a tethered mode, but can also operate autonomously without a tether on benign slopes. Figure 8 highlights pertinent components of the vehicle:

As a concept, Axel has a number of distinct advantages over standard wheeled vehicles for extreme-terrain missions. Its tether, which provides mechanical and electrical support for

Figure 7: Axel: an extreme-terrain rover. Axel is shown sampling the bedrock with its on-board scientific instruments while rappelling down a sheer cliff face (left). Also shown is a close-up view of the in-use UV reflectance spectrometer and microscopic imager payload (right).

Figure 8: Axel design. Note the vehicle symmetry, allowing for both conventional and inverted mobility. “Grousers” - the extruded paddles visible on each wheel - allow the vehicle to operate in sandy or soft terrain. The central axle contains avionics and engineering sensors, while scientific instruments are housed in the wheel bays.

power and communication, allows it to rappel down rugged and highly sloped terrains without having to maintain line-of-sight with its host rover and without requiring to remain in direct sunlight for energy replenishment.

Actuators and sensors (relating to mobility) are contained within the central axle, while science instruments are located in the wheel hubs. This compact form factor gives rise to a very robust vehicle, a requirement when travelling in cluttered terrains. The wheels are augmented with large grousers, ensuring that mobility is not compromised in soft or sandy terrain while providing an ability to overcome obstacles that are a wheel radius in height. A rounded wheel design ensures a positive stability point; the rover is inclined to return to its nominal orientation after a tipping event.

The simplicity of Axel’s design does not constrain its operation, however, and the vehicle is capable of traversing gulleys, ravines, escarpments, and navigating cliffs and overhangs - in short the type of geologically appealing areas highlighted in Figures 3 and 4. Table 1 lists the advantages and disadvantages of extreme-terrain mobility as a concept.

In the following sections, we compare and contrast different approaches to incorporating Axel into the SRL architecture.

Advantages

Expands science capability
Enables steep slope access
Accommodates instruments inside wheels
Technology demonstrator

Disadvantages

Increases mass/complexity/cost
Presents new engineering challenges:
- Docking/undocking
- Miniaturized avionics
- Thermal management

Table 1: Benefits/Risks of extreme-terrain science

4. ETM WITHIN SRL

The prime operating mode for Axel is to run tethered to a parent rover. However, Axel can also be operated autonomously, or in conjunction with other Axel units [8]. This versatility means Axel can be deployed as a payload, or as a component of another rover. We explore each of these configurations, and variants thereof, in the following sections.

Axel and mobileMAV

Building on the mobileMAV concept, the most basic way to integrate extreme-terrain capability is to utilise Axel as a payload vehicle, functioning essentially as a highly capable science instrument. Figure 9 illustrates this concept. Visible in the figure are various common elements: the Multi-Mission Radioisotope Thermoelectric Generator (MMRTG) located at the rear, the MSL-like rocker-bogie system (highlighted in blue) and the MAV envelope (green).

Figure 9: A small Axel vehicle concept (lower-right), as a payload of a larger mobileMAV. Visible are the MAV envelope (green), and the rocker-bogie mobility system.

The advantage of this approach is that it would be applicable to any SRL rover design capable of accommodating an additional 10-20 kg payload. The scaled size of Axel, however, means that the available capacity for extended-phase science instruments would be approximately 1-2kg. Additionally, the down-slope rappelling range of the vehicle would be limited (given the restricted spool radius) to tens of meters. Although broadly applicable to SRL concepts, this is the most limited form of extreme-terrain science.

An alternative to using Axel as a payload is to incorporate it as a fundamental component of the mobility system; this is shown in Figure 10:

Figure 10: Axel as a constituent component of the SRL rover mobility system. The full-scale Axel allows for increased science capabilities, as compared to its payload counterpart.

Here Axel is shown incorporated into an MSL-like rover serving as 2 of the rovers 6 wheels. This nominally-sized Axel is capable of carrying 6-10 kg of science instrumentation, and can rappel hundreds of meters downslope. However, the diameter of Axels wheels, sized for mobility, make packaging within the aeroshell complex. In both of these configurations, the mobileMAV vehicle is required to survive the MAV launch.

Axel and “Fetch”

Axel can also be incorporated into the “fetch” rover concept, as is illustrated in Figure 11:

Figure 11: Axel as a component of the “fetch” rover concept. This Axel design is larger than the payload version in Figure 9, but smaller than the full-size Axel in Figure 10.

This concept is, by definition, survivable post-MAV launch. The Axel depicted in the right-hand side of Figure 11 is a component of the rover mobility system, and is sized larger than the payload version in Figure 9, but smaller than the augmented mobility version shown in Figure 10. This means that the capabilities of “fetch” Axel are also scaled between these two extremes; available payload is approximately 2-3 kg of instruments, with an approximate tether length of 50-100m.

Size constraints do not allow for a MMRTG, and so power is supplied by solar panels. This imposes strict mission timeline constraints, and the round-trip distance may exceed this rovers capabilities.

Axel hybrid

This concept uses Axel as both a fundamental mobility component, as well as a dedicated extended-phase science rover, and is illustrated in Figure 12:

This rover would incorporate both Axel and MSL design elements. The rear wheels are MSL-like, while the Axel (center) and front wheels are fundamentally new designs. Visible in Figure 12 are the design envelopes of various constituent

Figure 12: The proposed Axel hybrid rover. Axel is located centrally in the mobility system, and is a constituent component of the proposed “separable MAV” concept.

components: the MMRTG (orange, rear of the rover), MAV (green, center) and avionics volume (blue, center). The MAV design envelope was fixed at a 2.3m vehicle, with a 0.6m diameter and 300kg landed mass.

The rover uses Axel as both a constituent mobility component, as well as a dedicated science rover in the extended phase, and is a constituent part of the “separable MAV” approach. The core idea is to separate the MAV, front wheels, and associated support structure as a stand-alone launch system. The Axel, central module, and rear wheels then form the basis of the extended-phase rover. Table 2 summarises the advantages and disadvantages of this approach.

Advantages

- Is inherently survivable rover, post-launch
- Can accommodate more sensitive instruments on the rover
- Contingency options for retrieving the cache (pre-, or post-MAV separation)
- Provide video of MAV launch (A mission-critical event)

Disadvantages

- Increases mass/complexity/cost
 - Risk of failed MAV separation
 - Requires thermal management post-separation
-

Table 2: Benefits/Risks of the separable-MAV concept

5. MISSION SEQUENCE

This paper assumes that the initial phases of the SRL mission - launch and cruise - could be similar, if not identical to that of MSL. For the purpose of this study, the launch vehicle is assumed to be class-equivalent to the Atlas-V 541 that was used to launch MSL. In the following sections, we briefly detail each mission stage, before focusing on the MAV deployment and launch.

Launch and cruise

Figure 13 depicts the rover in the “stowed” configuration for launch and cruise. The usable payload volume of the existing aeroshell requires design compromises with respect to the optimal design point for the Axel vehicle. In particular, accommodation within the aeroshell is only possible with an *increase* in the Axel baseline (allowing the wheels to conform better to the aeroshell wall), leading to a vehicle which is very stable, but less maneuverable than optimal. However, this limitation is alleviated with any increase in aeroshell

diameter.

Figure 13: Rover concept in a stowed configuration. The Axel and front wheels are both pivoted to conform to the aeroshell profile, and the sensing mast is horizontal.

Figure 14 shows the vehicle in the stowed configuration inside the aeroshell volume (rendered in yellow).

Figure 14: Rover in the stowed configuration, rendered inside the aeroshell usable volume

Touchdown

Figure 15: Rover in touchdown configuration. The Axel and front wheels have pivoted to their nominal operating position. Notable in this figure are the Bridle Exit Guides (BEGs, indicated in yellow) responsible for managing the interface between the rover and Skycrane. Placement of the axially-aligned MAV requires minor position changes from MSL.

Given the landed mass of the vehicle, and in order to leverage flight-validated designs, EDL would be accomplished through the Skycrane architecture - Figure 15 shows the rover

in “touchdown” mode. After jettisoning the heat shield, and in terminal descent, the central Axel and front wheels pivot down, and the rear wheels outward. As with similar large-rover missions (MSL, Mars 2020) the descent impact would be absorbed by the rover through the wheels and suspension system. Note the position of the descent anchor points in Figure 15 - these differ from those of MSL to accommodate the large axially-aligned MAV.

Traverse

Figure 16: Rover concept in traverse mode. The front and rear wheels have been pivoted to face the forward driving direction, and the mast has been extended.

Once the rover has touched-down, and post-landing activities have been finalized, the rover reconfigures into its “traverse” mode, as shown in Figure 16. This requires the front and rear wheels to be reoriented from the touchdown position. The rover would then perform the single-leg traverse to the cache site and, once at the site, uses the manipulation system to insert the cache into the MAV. In the interest of space, we do not perform a full analysis of this phase in terms of traversability guarantees, power-usage etc., and instead focus on the next three phases of the mission which depart substantially from previously considered deployments, and are worth considering in detail.

6. DEPLOYMENT

Conventional approaches to MAV deployment focus on the use of a single-shot erector mechanism, which lifts the MAV to its launch attitude. Given the unique characteristics of Axel, we seek to develop a deployment method where the motion of the vehicle itself can be used to orient the MAV. In this way, we are not encumbered by a complex single-use mechanism (that is also a potential single point-of-failure for the mission concept). A key advantage here is that we are not constrained to a 90° launch angle; the MAV can be successfully launched into orbit at angles as shallow as 20°. Figure 17 shows an overhead view of the initial configuration of the rover, before deploying the MAV:

We assume that the rover is now at the launch site, having successfully retrieved the cache and inserted it into the MAV. Again, we are not focusing on the traversal/retrieval portion of the mission as that would be similar to such a mobileMAV architecture that does not include the extreme terrain mobility component.

With the main body of the rover stationary, the front two

Figure 17: MAV deployment: Stage 1, top-view (left), side-view (right). The rover has reached the cache site and the cache has been inserted into the MAV, ready for deployment and launch.

wheels begin to move forward. As they are attached to the MAV, this results in a slow, controlled extraction of the launch vehicle from its storage bay. The body of Axel simultaneously begins to rotate, independent of the wheels - this provides an assistive, tractive force. The combined pull of the front wheels in conjunction with the Axel body rotation ensures redundancy in the event of failures with either two of the systems. Figure 18 illustrates this stage.

We again make use of Axels unique design and leverage the body rotation to place the MAV on the surface. A variety of methods can be utilised to accomplish this placing action, converting the pure rotation into constrained rectilinear motion.

Figure 18: MAV deployment: Stage 2. The front wheels begin to move forward, slowly extracting the MAV from its payload bed. The Axel begins to rotate its center body, providing an assistive tractive force on the MAV. At the fullest extent, Axel uses the body rotation to place the MAV in a controlled fashion on the surface.

As a prototype point-solution,

Once the vehicle is resting stably on the surface, the rear section of the rover would be free to leave the launch site and conduct the extreme-terrain mission, as shown in 20.

Figure 19: A prototype solution for placing the MAV system on the surface. The mechanism is rotated by the Axel-body - when the MAV cradle is at maximum extension, pins engage with the mechanism, which (through a hydraulic spring) ensure a gentle deployment onto the surface.

Figure 20: MAV deployment: Stage 3. The MAV has been placed on the terrain at a fixed launch attitude. The rover would be free to leave the launch area and conduct the extended-phase.

A preliminary proof-of-concept prototype based on existing hardware components has successfully demonstrated the separation of the MAV from the rover.

A pertinent point to note here is that the launch angle of the MAV would be dictated by the geometry of the vehicle, and the terrain of the launch site. However, given the broad launch window (between 20° and 90°) this is not a limiting factor of the system. We must, however, consider the case where the MAV cannot be launched immediately and must be thermally managed by the rover until launch.

Thermal considerations

Thermal analysis shows that, without active thermal management, the MAV would only survive 15 — 60 minutes post-separation. The driving case for this analysis is the deployment of the MAV on the surface during Martian winter at 30°S . As such, the following sections explore the options for regulating the thermal conditions of the MAV whilst deployed on the surface.

Tether and resistive heaters—Thermal control of the MAV through a tether is the most direct of the heating strategies. The mass/volume associated with the system is contained within the rover, and heat can be supplied for as long as is required. However, the tether required scales with the distance

(a) Traverse

(b) Extract start

(c) Extract end

(d) Deploy

Figure 21: An experimental evaluation of the hybrid rover, using existing Axel hardware. Figure (a) shows the initial “traverse” configuration, (b) the beginning of the MAV extraction, (c) the final stage of the MAV extraction before the deployment onto the surface, and (d) the position of both vehicles and the MAV after successful deployment.

to the MAV, and the system requires a spooling mechanism, pyro-disconnect, and other complex mechanisms.

Battery and resistive heaters—Battery heaters on the MAV do not require rover power; however, use of the MMRTG as a primary power source reduces the impact of this advantage. This solution incurs the highest mass cost, with battery mass estimated to be as high as 14-24kg. Use of batteries also limits the time that the MAV can be heated once deployed.

Chemical heaters—Chemical heaters are another solution that does not require a direct umbilical to the rover, but in all other aspects - mass, volume, heating duration - compare unfavorably to the previous two options, and as such are the least favored solution.

7. AXEL HYBRID SUBSYSTEMS

The following sections detail each of the constituent subsystems of the vehicle.

Power

One constraint driver for all SRL designs is the total traverse distance, from touchdown to MAV launch. For the “fetch” rover concept, this distance is double that of the “mobileMAV” - albeit with reduced complexity. In contrast to previous studies [1], we explicitly assume the use of an MMRTG. The energy profile of the MMRTG allows for extended drive times (if enabled by associated improvements in navigation), in addition to providing a thermal source for both MAV and rover heating.

Navigation and perception

Perception for the rover would be provided by an MSL-like mast, accommodating a similar NavCam arrangement [9]. This proposed mast is visible in Figure 16. Given the rover’s focus on sample retrieval and launch, there would be fewer accommodations for science instruments (apart from those proposed for the extended phase, which are Axel-centric). This would drive down both the required mass and volume of the mast. For instance, where the MSL Remote Sensing Mast (RSM) has two MastCams as science instruments in addition to two pairs of NavCam engineering cameras, we only require access to a redundant pair of NavCams.

Avionics

Given the large MAV payload and fixed envelope constraint (as dictated by the aeroshell), there would be a correspondingly smaller avionics volume as compared to an MSL baseline. To accommodate the smaller avionics volume and corresponding mass, several changes would be necessary for the avionics system. These include the miniaturization of the computation stack and the migration of the centralized motor controllers to distributed ones. The cold-capable motor drivers would then be co-located next to their corresponding actuator. The separable nature of the Axel rappelling rover from the rest of the rover necessitates separate avionics that are connected through an umbilical to the main avionics, power and communication subsystems. The inherently distributed nature of the avionics allows for a hybrid strategy that distributes computing between the main rover and the Axel, potentially allowing a further reduction in the needed volume for avionics. Given the projected date for a such mission, such advanced in flight avionics are expected to also reduce their required footprint.

Utilizing single-string architectures in both the WEB and the Axel reduces overall volume, while cross-strapping² would provide an overall redundant fall-back system. In addition, we propose the use of low-mass/low-power System-on-a-Chip (SoC) computing architectures for both avionics payloads.

²Cross-strapping in this context means full connectivity of avionics and sensors, imparting redundancy if one module should fail.

Communications

Telecommunications on the rover bears similarity to that of MSL, with a high-gain X-band antenna used for earth-based communication, and a UHF antenna for communication with the orbiting Mars network of satellites. Data rates are assumed to match those of previous studies [1], which are 438-1120bps/2kbps transmit receive and 2Mbps/64kbps transmit/receive for the X-band and HGA respectively.

Manipulation

The vehicle would be equipped with a modified MSL-like 5-DOF arm, with improved 3.2m reach. The requirements for the cache-retrieval manipulation system are less stringent than for MSL - in particular because of the lack of pre-load required for drilling operations. The arm would be augmented with an end-effector and cameras suitable for assisting with cache retrieval.

8. MASS EQUIPMENT LIST

Table 3 compares the Mass Equipment List (MEL) for power elements (producer/consumer) of the hybrid rover and MSL baseline. Both rovers utilize MMRTGs and batteries; however the hybrid rover batteries are distributed between the WEB and Axel, whereas they are completely contained in the WEB for MSL.

	Mass (kg) (Hybrid)	Mass (kg) (MSL)
Power Sources		
Radioactive Power Sources (RPS)	45	45
WEB Batteries	20	26.7
Axel Batteries	6	-
Subtotal	71	71.7
Power Consumers		
Power management	21	30.4
Computing elements	2	23.8
Motor controllers	4	27.1
Harnessing	20	50.1
Guidance, Navigation and Control	8	8
X-band communication	16.8	16.8
UHF communication	7.3	7.3
Subtotal	79.1	163.5
Axel Avionics		
Power management	5	-
Main compute element	2	-
Motor controllers	2	-
Subtotal	9	
Total	159.1	234.7

Table 3: Mass Equipment List (MEL) for the hybrid rover, and MSL baseline. Values are approximate, and used solely for the purposes of comparison.

As can be seen in Table 3, the hybrid rover benefits substantially from next-generation avionics. Table 4 details the mass breakdown for the mechanical systems, and highlights the mass distribution of the two systems. The hybrid concept’s heavier mobility system enables a post-MAV mission with compelling science potential.

	Mass (kg) (Hybrid)	Mass (kg) (MSL)
Mechanical (Common)		
Rover structure	175	169
Rover mobility	90	217
Rover mast	20	43
Separation systems	5.1	5.1
Rover-mounted CEDL equipment	8.8	6.8
Rover-balance mass	20	13
Subtotal	318.9	453.9
Mechanical (Axel)		
Axel	60	-
Front wheels, structure, separation	100	-
Docking mechanism, anchoring	70	-
Subtotal	230	-
Thermal		
	42	42
MAV		
	300	-
Sampling/Instruments		
Arm and sample handling	90	117.4
Payload science instruments	40	73.7
Subtotal	130	191.1
Total	1020.9	687
Grand Total	1180	921.7

Table 4: Mass breakdown for mechanical systems: Hybrid rover concept (left column), MSL (right column).

9. CHALLENGES

Adopting a new mobility system has a number of advantages, as outlined in the previous sections. However, foregoing the use of heritage, flight-validated hardware increases the complexity (and cost) of the proposed design.

Utilizing Axel as a mobility system allows for both the fulfillment of the primary mission requirement *and* the extended-phase, although this conceptual design shows that there is an associated mass penalty.

The proposed Axel hinging mechanism interferes with the current spool/tether management system, located in the center

of the rover. Further work is required on alternate packaging strategies and/or hinge placement to allow for both hinging and a spool.

As detailed previously, the aeroshell profile drives the width of Axel to a minimum of 2.8 m, making maneuvering in extreme terrain more challenging. However, the large wheel-to-wheel lateral baseline results in a very stable rover robust to tipping.

The docking/undocking operation of Axel in the extended phase poses some unique challenges; for instance, how to dock repeatedly, robustly and autonomously over extended periods. Recent research into this issue [10] has shown that the challenge is not insurmountable.

We also explicitly require the use of miniaturized avionics, given the need to accommodate the large MAV profile without a corresponding increase in aeroshell volume. However, given the hypothetical launch window for the SRL concept, we expect advances in avionics to make this achievable.

10. CONCLUSIONS

We have summarized several options for augmenting the SRL mission concept with a capability that would enable the exploration of scientifically-compelling sites in the potential extended phase of the mission post MAV launch. We have outlined the benefits and risk of several such configuration options. For the Hybrid Rover option, we have examined how this augmentation would allow for the separation of the MAV prior to launch, thus ensuring a survivable and fully operational rover post launch, as well as augment the rover with an extreme-terrain exploration capability to target these scientifically compelling sites.

Comparing and contrasting the hybrid vehicle to existing mobility systems would require the design and build of a full-scale prototype. This would allow for a full characterization of the mobility characteristics across a breadth of terrains. Repeated sampling excursions using Axel requires the development of a robust tether management system, that is compatible with the folded Axel design. Given that Axel would not be caching any scientific data for future missions, it is necessary to demonstrate the in-situ experiment pipeline, including contingency sample acquisition and handling.

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